

**PERCEPTION OF THE SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS ON THE
PARTICIPATION OF THE STAKEHOLDERS TO THE
IMPLEMENTATION OF SCHOOL-BASED
MANAGEMENT IN THE SCHOOLS
DIVISION OF ZAMBALES**

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Perception of the School Administrators on the Participation of the Stakeholders to the Implementation of School-Based Management in the Schools Division of Zambales

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Abstract

The cornerstone of school-based management is delegating greater authority to schools. It plays an essential role in the empowerment of school communities towards continuous improvement aimed at providing the learners quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education. This accounts for the collaborative efforts of the school and the community in the preparation of school improvement plan. It is a network which guides the education system to achieve its shared vision, mission and goals making them responsive and relevant to the context of diverse environment. Findings reveal that: 1) Majority of the respondents are from Sta Cruz District, the size of the school is medium with below 500 enrollees and practicing SBM Level 2 with 0-4 non-teaching personnel. Stakeholders are alumni of their own school; 2) The perceptions of the respondents towards leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management resources were perceived to be Strongly Agree (A); 3) There is highly significant difference on the perceived level of participation of the stakeholders to the school-based management when grouped according to district. However, there are no significant differences with regards to school size, SBM level of practice, no. of non-teaching personnel, total no. of enrollees, and stakeholders.

Keywords: *school-based management, stakeholders, perception*

Introduction

The proverb "It takes a village to raise a child" underscores the vital role of community involvement in education. Beyond parents and family, the broader community shares responsibility for ensuring high-quality education for all students. A quality education system meets individual school goals, addresses student and societal needs, and fosters 21st-century skills acquisition. School-Based Management (SBM) has emerged as an effective approach to improve education by increasing school staff autonomy in decision-making. Implemented globally, SBM has proven effective in realizing educational goals in various countries. In the Philippines, SBM is a key component of the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA), aimed at achieving Education for All (EFA) objectives.

Research over the past decades has revealed that SBM contributes significantly to improvements in student achievements. SBM empowers local schools in decision-making, giving school stakeholders greater power and authority to manage their schools. The implementation of SBM has redefined the roles of principals.

Instead of traditional, legal, and functional authority, principals are now encouraged to build policies that promote community participation and collaboration. Successful school leaders must adopt various leadership styles, including transformational, ethical, situational, and authentic leadership.

The conceptual framework of this study is grounded in the "Theory of School-Based Management," which covers practical strategies for school administrators, the power of school-based leadership, and SBM implementation. This theory employs concepts of "equifinality" and "decentralization," assuming that "school is a self-managing system" and emphasizing the "initiative of human factor" and "improvement of internal process."

This study investigates the perception of school administrators on stakeholder participation in the implementation of School-Based Management (SBM). The research aims to describe the profile of the schools in terms of district, school size, SBM level of practice, number of non-teaching personnel, total number of enrollees, and stakeholders. It also assesses the perception of school administrators on the level of stakeholder participation in SBM principles, including leadership and governance, management of resources, curriculum and instruction, and accountability and continuous improvement. Furthermore, it explores the implications of this study for school administrators' perceptions of stakeholder participation in SBM.

The findings of this study will be valuable to DepEd Officials by providing insights into the current state of SBM implementation and its implications for school management systems. School Administrators will benefit from evaluating the level of partnership developed with stakeholders and identifying areas for improvement. Stakeholders will gain awareness of their crucial role in the educational system and be encouraged to form stronger partnerships with schools. Students will benefit as their personal success remains a priority for school administrators and stakeholders. Future Researchers can use this study as a reference and guide for further studies in this field.

The study was conducted in selected schools in the Division of Zambales, Philippines. It included secondary and elementary schools with varying levels of SBM practice. By addressing these objectives within the specified scope, this research aims to contribute to the understanding and improvement of stakeholder participation in School-Based Management, ultimately enhancing the quality of education in the Philippines.

Methodology

This study employs a descriptive survey research approach to investigate the level of stakeholder participation in school-based management implementation within the Division of Zambales. Descriptive research aims to present facts concerning the nature of a group, object, condition, or phenomenon, making it suitable for examining the varying conditions among different objects of study. The research targets school administrators, expecting to enhance their service excellence through collaboration with community stakeholders.

The study's respondents comprise principals and administrators from selected schools in the Division of Zambales, encompassing various levels of School-Based Management (SBM) practice across secondary and elementary institutions. To support the data provided by the main respondents, the researcher conducted random interviews with stakeholders.

Purposive sampling was utilized to select the sample, relying on the researcher's judgment to identify participants who could provide the necessary data. This non-probability sampling technique is particularly useful when the sample size is relatively small compared to probability sampling methods. The research aims to determine school administrators' perceptions of stakeholder participation in SBM implementation using researcher-developed questionnaires administered to the sample respondents.

The primary data sources include school administrators, who were asked to present Modes of Verification (MOVs) to support their survey responses when necessary. Stakeholders were also randomly interviewed at each school to substantiate the required data. The research instrument, formulated based on the SBM Assessment Tool used during SBM Validation in the Schools Division of Zambales, consists of two parts: the school's demographic profile and the administrators' perceptions of stakeholder participation in SBM implementation.

To facilitate data gathering, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Zambales and consulted with the Senior Education Specialist for Research. The questionnaires were administered to the respondents within the division during the school year. The researcher personally asked school administrators to answer the instrument and conducted interviews for clarification. Data collection was followed by tabulation, analysis, and interpretation.

Ethical considerations were prioritized throughout the study. Participants were protected from harm, their dignity was respected, and informed consent was obtained. Privacy and confidentiality of research data were ensured, and anonymity of individuals and organizations was maintained. The researcher committed to honest and transparent communication, avoiding misleading information or biased presentation of findings.

Data analysis was conducted sequentially after retrieving the instruments. The level of stakeholder participation was consolidated through the questionnaires, and the data analysis was performed using SPSS v. 21. This comprehensive approach ensures a thorough examination of stakeholder participation in school-based management implementation within the Division of Zambales.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the school

District. Out of forty-five (45) respondents, District of Sta. Cruz got the highest frequency of twelve (12) with the percentage of 26.7. Next is Candelaria District having a frequency of seven (7) occupying 15.6 percent. Both District of Masinloc and Iba have the same frequency of four (4) with the percentage of 8.9 percent. This means that Sta.Cruz is a first-class municipality in the province of Zambales. According to the census 2015, it has a population of 58,151 people.

School Size. Medium size got the highest frequency of nineteen (19) with the percentage of 42.2 while small size got the lowest frequency of seven (7) with the percentage of 15.6.

SBM Level of Practice. The data gathered show that most of the principals/administrators were practicing SBM Level 1 and 2 having a frequency of twenty (20) or 43.5 percent. Next is the SBM level 3 having a frequency of six (6) with 13 percent (13%) respectively.

Number of Non-Teaching Personnel. The data shows that most of the schools has non-teaching personnel ranging from 0 – 4 having a frequency of twenty (20) or 44.4 percent while bracket 17 – 20 with 2.2 percent was the least number of non-teaching personnel.

Total Number of Enrollees. Most of the principals are handling below five hundred (500) enrollees having a frequency of twenty-two (22) or 48.9 percent. There were only 2.2 percent for enrollee bracket 4001 – 4500.

Stakeholders. The data shows that most of the stakeholders are alumni of the schools having a frequency of eighteen (18) or 40.0 percent. Next is Parents Teachers Association (PTA) occupying fifteen (15) or 33.3 percent. Seven (7) or 15.6 percent belong to LGU. Finally, fraternity is the least stakeholders with five (5) or 11.1 percent.

Perception on the Level of Participation of the Stakeholders

Leadership and Governance. Indicator 2 stated as “Stakeholders involve themselves in reviewing regularly the improvement of the development plan” obtained a weighted mean of 3.7556 and ranked 1.5; indicator 5 stated “Stakeholders attend and actively participate

on training and development” with a weighted mean of 3.7556 and ranked (1.5); and indicator 1 stated as “School stakeholders are leading/initiating the formation of organizational structures” with a weighted mean of 3.5556 and ranked 3rd. The computed weighted mean of indicators 2, 5 and 1 obtained a descriptive equivalent of Strongly Agree (SA) respectively. These were the top three as perceived by the respondents towards leadership and governance. Indicator 4 stated as “Stakeholders have access to school information” obtained a weighted mean of 3.5333 and ranked 4th and indicator 3 stated as “Stakeholders (PTA officers, Alumni, SGC, SPC, SBM, Working Committee, DRRM & Faculty Club) define and perform well of their roles and responsibilities” with a weighted mean of 3.1111 (Rank 5). The computed weighted mean of indicators 4 and 3 obtained a descriptive equivalent of Strongly Agree (SA) respectively. The computed overall weighted mean of their assessment was 3.5422 interpreted as Strongly Agree (SA).

Curriculum and Instructions. Indicator 2 stated as “Stakeholders allow the learners to use the community as a learning laboratory (e.g. school community livelihood projects) and copy localized/contextualized IMs/LMs.” obtained a weighted mean of 3.5556 and ranked 1.5; indicator 6 stated “Stakeholders nurture the value and environments that are protective of all children and demonstrate behaviour consistent to the organizations Vision, Mission and Goals.” with a weighted mean of 3.4444 and ranked (2); and indicator 1 stated as “Stakeholders support programs/projects addressing performance discrepancies/deficits/gaps e.g. school remedial program: assessment systems e.g. Phil-IRI, Numeracy test etc. and school benchmarking” with a weighted mean of 3.4000 and ranked 3rd. The computed weighted mean of indicators 2, and 1 obtained a descriptive equivalent of Strongly Agree (SA) respectively. These were the top three as perceived by the respondents towards curriculum and instruction. Indicator 3 stated as “Stakeholders regularly and collaboratively monitors learning systems to ensure holistic growth of the learners and the community” obtained a weighted mean of 3.3778 and ranked 4.5; indicator 5 stated as “Stakeholders help in assessing and reviewing of the assessment tools such as results are used for collaborative decision-making.” with a weighted mean of 3.3778 (Rank 4.5); indicator 7 stated “Stakeholders provide methods and resources that are learner and community-friendly, safe, inclusive accessible and aimed at developing self-directed learners” with a weighted mean of 3.1111 (Rank 6), and indicator 4 stated “Stakeholders develop the method and materials for developing creative thinking and problem solving” with a weighted mean of 3.2222. The computed weighted mean of indicators 3, 5, 7 and 4 obtained a descriptive equivalent of Strongly Agree (SA) respectively. The computed overall weighted mean of their assessment was 3.3841 interpreted as Strongly Agree (SA).

Accountability and Continuous Improvement. Indicator 2 stated as “Stakeholders provide feedback and actively participate to develop performance accountability system” obtained a weighted mean of 3.6444 and ranked 1st; indicator 5 stated “Participatory assessment of performance is done regularly with the community” with a weighted mean of 3.5556 and ranked (2); and indicator 4 stated as “Stakeholders are accountable in the continuous enhancement of management structures and mechanisms that are responsive to the emerging needs and demands of the community” with a weighted mean of 3.4889 and ranked 3rd. The computed weighted mean of indicators 2, 5 and 4 obtained a descriptive equivalent of Strongly Agree (SA) respectively. These were the top three as perceived by the respondents towards accountability and continuous improvement. Indicator 3 stated as “Stakeholders are accountable in the continuous enhancement of management structures and mechanisms that are responsive to the emerging needs and demands of the community” obtained a weighted mean of 3.4222 and ranked 4th; and indicator 1 stated as “Community stakeholders clearly define and agree upon on the roles and responsibilities of accountable person/s and collective body/ies” with a weighted mean of 3.3333 (Rank 5). The computed weighted mean of indicators 3, and 1 obtained a descriptive equivalent of Strongly Agree (SA) respectively. The computed overall weighted mean of their assessment was 3.4889 interpreted as Strongly Agree (SA).

Management of Resources. Indicator 2 stated as “Stakeholders engage in regular dialogue for planning and resource programming that is accessible and inclusive and support implementation of community education plans” obtained a weighted mean of 3.6889 and ranked 1st; indicator 4 stated “Stakeholders regularly monitor and evaluate, and report processes of resource management together with the learning managers, facilitators and community stakeholders” with a weighted mean of 3.5778 and ranked (2.5); and indicator 5 stated as “Partnership with stakeholders is strengthened and sustained for improving resource management” with a weighted mean of 3.5778 and ranked 2.5th. The computed weighted mean of indicators 2, 4 and 5 obtained a descriptive equivalent of Strongly Agree (SA) respectively. These were the top three as perceived by the respondents towards accountability and continuous improvement. Indicator 1 stated as “Stakeholders participate in regular source inventory as basis for resource allocation and mobilization” obtained a weighted mean of 3.5111 and ranked 4th; and indicator 3 stated as “Stakeholders possess appropriate behaviors to ensure judicious, appropriate and effective use of resources” with a weighted mean of 3.4222 (Rank 5). The computed weighted mean of indicators 1 and 3 obtained a descriptive equivalent of Strongly Agree (SA) respectively. The computed overall weighted mean of their assessment was 3.5556 interpreted as Strongly Agree (SA).

Analysis on the Difference in Perception of the School Administrators on the participation of the Stakeholders to the School-Based Management when grouped according to Profile Variables

The data showed that there was a significant difference on the perception of respondents on the participation of the stakeholders to the school-based management when grouped according to district. The computed F values are greater than the tabular F value (2.55) at 0.05 level of significance. This was supported by a p-value less than the 0.05 level of significance. The data provide sufficient evidence to conclude that there is a significant difference on the participation of stakeholders in the school-based management with regards to district. It was not significantly different on the perception of respondents on the participation of the stakeholders to the school-based management when grouped according to school size. The computed F values are lesser than the tabular F value (2.83) at 0.05 level of

significance. This was supported by a p-value greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The data provide sufficient evidence to conclude that there is no significant difference on the participation of stakeholders in the school-based management with regards to school size. Likewise on the perception of respondents on the participation of the stakeholders to the school-based management when grouped according to SBM level of practice. The computed F values are lesser than the tabular F value (3.22) at 0.05 level of significance. This was supported by a p-value greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The data provide sufficient evidence to conclude that there is no significant difference on the participation of stakeholders in the school-based management with regards to SBM level of practice. Also, it was not significantly different on the perception of respondents on the participation of the stakeholders to the school-based management when grouped according to number of non-teaching personnel. The computed F values are lesser than the tabular F value (2.21) at 0.05 level of significance. This was supported by a p-value greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The data provide sufficient evidence to conclude that there is no significant difference on the participation of stakeholders in the school-based management with regards to number of non-teaching personnel. There is no significant difference on the perception of respondents on the participation of the stakeholders to the school-based management when grouped according to total number of enrollees. The computed F values are lesser than the tabular F value (2.45) at 0.05 level of significance. This was supported by a p-value greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The data provide sufficient evidence to conclude that there is no significant difference on the participation of stakeholders in the school-based management with regards total number of enrollees. The perception of respondents on the participation of the stakeholders to the school-based management when grouped according to stakeholders is not statistically significant. The computed F values are lesser than the tabular F value (2.83) at 0.05 level of significance. This was supported by a p-value greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The data provide sufficient evidence to conclude that there is no significant difference on the participation of stakeholders in the school-based management.

Implications of the Study to the SBM Perception of School Administrators to the Participation of the Stakeholders

This study on school administrators' perceptions of stakeholder participation in School-Based Management (SBM) is likely to have significant and far-reaching implications. It may lead to an enhanced understanding of stakeholder roles, helping administrators recognize the varied ways different groups can contribute to school management. The research could identify best practices in stakeholder engagement, potentially improving strategies for involving stakeholders in decision-making processes. Communication strategies between administrators and stakeholders may be refined, leading to more effective information sharing and engagement. Recognizing the diversity of school profiles, administrators might learn to tailor their approaches to stakeholder engagement based on their specific contexts. The findings could inform professional development programs for school administrators, focusing on skills needed for effective SBM implementation and stakeholder engagement. At a broader level, the study might influence policy refinements in the Department of Education, potentially leading to more supportive frameworks for SBM implementation. A shift in leadership paradigm from traditional top-down models to more collaborative, participatory styles that value stakeholder input may occur. The study could influence resource allocation, with potentially greater emphasis on stakeholder engagement activities. New accountability measures might emerge, focusing more on stakeholder participation metrics. Community relations could be strengthened as administrators recognize the value of community support in achieving educational goals. Ultimately, if the study shows a positive correlation between stakeholder participation and school performance, it could lead to increased efforts to engage stakeholders as a means of improving student outcomes. These implications suggest that the study has the potential to significantly influence how school administrators perceive and approach stakeholder participation in SBM, potentially leading to more effective and inclusive school management practices across the Division of Zambales and beyond.

Conclusions

Based on the investigation's findings, the researcher concludes that the majority of respondents are from the Sta Cruz District, representing medium-sized schools with fewer than 500 enrollees and practicing SBM Level 2 with 0-4 non-teaching personnel. Alumni of the respective schools constitute a significant portion of the stakeholders. The respondents strongly agree with the perceptions towards leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management resources. A highly significant difference exists in the perceived level of stakeholder participation in school-based management when grouped according to district. However, no significant differences were found concerning school size, SBM level of practice, number of non-teaching personnel, total number of enrollees, and stakeholders.

In light of these findings, the researcher recommends that the harmonious and strong relationship between school administrators and stakeholders be sustained to enhance school-based management. School administrators are encouraged to develop policies that promote participation and collaboration in providing quality education. Furthermore, schools are urged to strive for a high level of School-based Management practice through combined efforts of the school and community, with the ultimate goal of improving student achievement. These recommendations aim to build upon the positive perceptions of stakeholder participation and address the variations observed across different districts, fostering a more consistent and effective implementation of School-based Management across all schools.

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